

Ti₄₀Zr₁₀Cu₃₆Pd₁₄ bulk metallic glass as oral implant material

Amir Rezvan^{a,b}, Elham Sharifikolouei^c, Viktor Soprunyuk^d, Wilfried Schranz^d, Juraj Todt^b, Alice Lassnig^a, Christoph Gammer^a, Nikolaus August Sifferlinger^e, Atacan Asci^b, Ilya Okulov^{f,g}, Sandra Schlögl^h, Jozef Keckes^b, Ziba Najmiⁱ, Andrea Cochisⁱ, Alessandro Calogero Scaliaⁱ, Lia Rimondiniⁱ, Baran Sarac^{a,*}, Jürgen Eckert^{a,b}

^a Erich Schmid Institute of Materials Science, Austrian Academy of Sciences, Jahnstraße 12, A-8700 Leoben, Austria

^b Department of Materials Science, Chair of Materials Physics, Montanuniversität Leoben, Jahnstraße 12, A-8700 Leoben, Austria

^c Department of Applied Science and Technology, Politecnico di Torino, Corso Duca Degli Abruzzi 24, 10129, Turin TO, Italy

^d University of Vienna, Faculty of Physics, Physics of Functional Materials, Boltzmanngasse 5, A-1090 Vienna, Austria

^e Department of Mineral Resources Engineering, Chair of Mining Engineering and Mineral Economics, Montanuniversität Leoben, Franz-Josef-Straße 18, A-8700 Leoben, Austria

^f Leibniz Institute for Materials Engineering – IWT, Badgasteinerstraße 3, 28359 Bremen, Germany

^g Faculty of Production Engineering University of Bremen, Badgasteinerstraße 1, 28359 Bremen, Germany

^h Polymer Competence Center Leoben GmbH, Rosergerstraße 12, 8700 Leoben, Austria

ⁱ Department of Health Sciences, Center for Translational Research on Autoimmune and Allergic Diseases – CAAD, Università del Piemonte Orientale UPO, Corso Trieste 15/A, 28100 Novara, NO, Italy

ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Bulk metallic glass
Structure
Mechanical performance
Viscoelastic behavior
Thermoplastic net-shaping
Cytocompatible
Oral implant

ABSTRACT

The application of highly biocompatible advanced materials leads to fewer complications and more successful medical treatments. This study proposes Ti₄₀Zr₁₀Cu₃₆Pd₁₄ bulk metallic glass (BMG) as an oral implant material and provides insights into its possible processing routes, where high-temperature compression molding via an optimized process is adopted to both evaluate the thermoplastic net-shaping kinetics and tune the specific properties of the alloy. We present processed BMGs and BMG composites of the same composition with improved thermomechanical stability, from which high strength retention at temperatures, compared to the cast glass, by above 100 K higher is registered via dynamic mechanical analysis. ~100 nm thin surface layers comprised of Ti, Cu, and Zr oxides form at the surface of the alloys, as identified by high-resolution transmission microscopy. Also, ~4 orders of magnitude lower passivation current density along with ~2 orders of magnitude lower corrosion current density of the processed glass compared to the values of the as-cast state confirms an extremely high stability in a 0.9 wt% saline environment which can be linked to surface hydrophobicity. Cytocompatibility analysis conducted by seeding human gingival fibroblast cells directly onto the thermoplastically formed Ti₄₀Zr₁₀Cu₃₆Pd₁₄ BMG reveals no adverse effect on cytocompatibility. On the other hand, the formation of a nanoscale oxide layer on the thermoplastically formed samples leads to significantly higher cell attachments on the surface.

1. Introduction

Considering the demand for functional materials that can be used in biomedical applications, surface topography becomes important, thereby processing and net-shaping of materials. The disadvantage of most crystalline metals is that they possess strength values of either above 100 MPa or below 10⁻⁷ MPa. They pass the in-between values with their phase transition from a solid to a liquid state [1]. Bulk

metallic glasses (BMGs) grant access to an ideal processing region, in which glassy metals with a strength of <10⁻⁷ MPa and a viscosity of 10³ – 10⁸ Pa s can be processed like plastics [2].

The drawback of direct casting of BMGs is the limitation to simple shapes, such as rods and plates. Thermoplastic net-shaping (TPN) is a two-step process where the casting and forming steps of BMGs are decoupled [3,4]. Thereby the cast piece undergoes deformation after it is heated close to the crystallization temperature (T_x), the region where

* Corresponding author.

E-mail address: baransarac@gmail.com (B. Sarac).

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.matdes.2023.112256>

Received 4 June 2023; Received in revised form 13 July 2023; Accepted 15 August 2023

Available online 16 August 2023

0264-1275/© 2023 The Authors. Published by Elsevier Ltd. This is an open access article under the CC BY license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

BMGs show their highest deformability. From an engineering viewpoint, the surface micro-patterning of BMGs can be achieved by TPN in the supercooled liquid region (SCLR), by which hierarchically modulated surfaces of high complexity can be generated [4–7]. However, marginal glass-forming ability and the high susceptibility of specific types of BMGs towards oxidation result in limited formability when formed into microcavities, where the resistance against flow restricts the desired patterns to bump-shaped microfeatures with controlled height and rounded corners [8]. Moreover, crystallization has to be avoided. Crystallization limits the processing time for a hot-forming operation since the flow stress in crystalline materials is orders of magnitude higher than in the supercooled liquid region (SCLR) [9]. An appealing characteristic of metallic glasses is that the crystallization kinetics in the SCLR is sluggish. This allows excellent net-shape processing on a convenient time scale, i.e., the material can be deformed within a rather large time window [2].

The assessment of the viscoelastic behavior of glasses under controlled laboratory conditions is an approach to estimate how the materials could respond in harsh environments. A suitable technique is dynamic mechanical analysis (DMA), conveying information about the thermo-mechanically driven structural relaxation and crystallization behavior in advanced glassy multicomponent systems.

The life expectancy in industrialized countries has increased in the last decades and, consequently, the necessity for restorative medicine. In this context, dental implants and medical devices are strong emerging economic fields. When it comes to oral implants, there are several parameters at force to consider. The direct biocompatibility is evaluated by the cell adhesion and proliferation on the surface, and indirect cytocompatibility is connected to the corrosion and wear resistance of the material. If the implant releases wear debris over time, it could cause inflammation on the surgery side leading to a retrieval of the implant. Additionally, with the advancement of functional biomaterials, there is a search for the development of antifouling implant surfaces. The most popular oral implants rely on Ti- and Zr-based alloys for their proven biocompatibility [10,11]. As mentioned before, metallic glasses have the advantage of improved oxidation and corrosion resistance compared with their crystalline counterparts, which in this case, is crucial to prevent inflammation in the long term [12,13]. In this regard, toxic-element free $\text{Ti}_{60}\text{Zr}_{20}\text{Si}_8\text{Ge}_7\text{B}_3\text{Sn}_2$ and $\text{Ti}_{50}\text{Zr}_{30}\text{Si}_8\text{Ge}_7\text{B}_3\text{Sn}_2$ metallic glasses have been reported to have higher pitting potential and a larger passivation domain coupled with outstanding cytocompatibility in contact with mesenchymal stem cells [14]. When it comes to antifouling properties, one of the most essential factors to control are the surface chemistry and topography. Bacteria with various physicochemical characteristics adhere differently to a given material, and the surface is the first place they encounter. In other words, depending on the bacteria's surface characteristics, which are defined by their genome, adhering bacteria might have a preference to adhere to hydrophobic or hydrophilic surfaces [15]. Sharifikolouei et al. [16] have used this approach to develop Zr-based metallic glasses with promising anti-fouling properties. One might say that the surface wettability of Ti-based metallic glasses such as $\text{Ti}_{40}\text{Zr}_{10}\text{Cu}_{36}\text{Pd}_{14}$ is similar to that of Ti-6Al-4V, i.e., the gold standard of oral implants. However, in our previous study [17], it was shown that the initial performance of $\text{Ti}_{40}\text{Zr}_{10}\text{Cu}_{36}\text{Pd}_{14}$ BMG is similar to Ti-6Al-4V for oral implants, but after an extended time, the formation of an oxide layer (TiO_2) on the surface of Ti-6Al-4V promotes a significantly higher oral biofilm formation. Additionally, $\text{Ti}_{40}\text{Zr}_{10}\text{Cu}_{36}\text{Pd}_{14}$ BMG has higher strength and lower Young's modulus compared with Ti-6Al-4V, which is beneficial to alleviate the stress-shielding effect [18–21], and lower ion release below the cytotoxicity threshold in artificial saliva solution [17].

In this work, the structural relaxation kinetics and crystallization behavior of $\text{Ti}_{40}\text{Zr}_{10}\text{Cu}_{36}\text{Pd}_{14}$ upon net-shaping is evaluated by a sensitive frequency-dependent DMA technique at elevated temperatures, which gives insights into the impact of thermoplastic net-shaping under certain conditions. The corrosion behavior of oxide-containing and

oxide-free fully glassy and partially crystallized, i.e., composite, samples are analyzed through potentiodynamic polarization and electrochemical impedance spectroscopy. The oxidation of the alloy is investigated by means of transmission electron microscopy-energy dispersive X-ray (TEM-EDX). Furthermore, the effect of the oxide layer formation on the cell cytocompatibility of $\text{Ti}_{40}\text{Zr}_{10}\text{Cu}_{36}\text{Pd}_{14}$ BMG is assessed by cultivating human gingival fibroblast (HGF) cells directly onto the specimen surfaces.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Materials preparation

2.1.1. Casting

A $\text{Ti}_{40}\text{Zr}_{10}\text{Cu}_{36}\text{Pd}_{14}$ master alloy was prepared in an Edmund Buehler AM0.5 arc melting system operated under a Ti-gettered argon atmosphere. The industrial-grade alloy constituents of 99.9% purity were weighed with an accuracy of ± 0.001 g. Rotary and diffusion pumps were utilized to evacuate the system down to 10^{-7} mbar. During melting, the melting current went up to a maximum of 160 A. To ensure homogeneity of the ingot, the melting was repeated four times. The alloy was cast afterwards into a copper mold with a rod geometry of 2 mm diameter and 50 mm length. The pressure gradient necessary for suction between the designed mold cavity and the working chamber was attained by purging argon. From the cast rods, pieces were cut for subsequent characterization.

2.1.2. Thermoplastic net-shaping

High-temperature compression molding was adopted to evaluate the thermoplastic net-shaping kinetics of the alloy, where the process parameters such as time, temperature, and pressure were optimized. The specimens ($\text{Ti}_{40}\text{Zr}_{10}\text{Cu}_{36}\text{Pd}_{14}$ BMG) were solid cylinder shapes ~ 3.5 mm in height and ~ 2 mm in diameter. They were heated to temperatures around 713 K then pressed axially by up to 10 kN with strain rates of 10^{-2} s^{-1} (TPN glass) and 10^{-3} s^{-1} (TPN composite), respectively within ~ 1 and ~ 11 min. The deformation in the course of heating was carried out under a vacuum of 10^{-4} mbar.

2.2. Materials characterization

2.2.1. Synchrotron XRD and TEM analyses

Structural analysis was carried out by high-energy synchrotron X-ray diffraction (XRD) in transmission geometry with a monochromatic beam of 14.23 pm wavelength. Two-dimensional diffraction patterns were collected on a Perkin Elmer XRD 1621 two-dimensional X-ray detector placed approx. 1.3 m downstream of the samples and were azimuthally integrated using the pyFAI software package [22]. The detector geometry was determined using a LaB_6 calibration standard and using the routines provided by pyFAI. Peak indexing was performed using the PDF-2 database (ICDD, Newton Square, USA) within EVA (Bruker AXS, Karlsruhe, Germany). Detailed structural analysis was carried out using TEM. Electron transparent lamellae of the surface region was created via focused ion beam (FIB) lift-out in a Zeiss Auriga workstation equipped with an Omniprobe micromanipulator. To protect the sample surface during FIB cutting a protective carbon layer and an amorphous W layer were deposited on top of the surface using the gas injection system (GIS) of the work station. Coarse trench cuts up to fine polishing of the lamellae were performed at an acceleration voltage of 30 kV and currents ranging from 2nA down to 50 pA. The TEM analyses were conducted in a JEOL 2200FS microscope at 200 kV, equipped with an Oxford Ultim Max EDX detector. The cross-sections were analyzed using scanning TEM mode, and the elemental compositions, depending on the sample interior and surface, were measured using EDX mapping.

2.2.2. DMA and TE

DMA was conducted using a Diamond DMA device (Perkin Elmer

Inc.) in 3-point bending mode within a temperature range from 300 K to 850 K while purging with N_2 gas continuously upon heating, a constant heating rate of 5 K min^{-1} was employed at frequencies of 0.1 to 1 to 10 Hz. The specimens had solid rectangular shapes of 5 mm in length, 2 mm in width, and 1 mm in thickness. The experiments were performed by imposing 10 N axial force in a displacement-controlled mode with a displacement oscillation amplitude of $5\text{ }\mu\text{m}$. At the test's domain, the maximum stress across the samples reached 30 N mm^{-2} . Thermal expansion/contraction (TE) was measured using a TMA-4000 device (Perkin Elmer Inc.) under a constant load of 50 mN. The specimens were heated from 300 K to 850 K. The heating/cooling rates were 5 K min^{-1} .

2.2.3. Electrochemical investigations

Electrochemical measurements were conducted in a three-electrode glass cell at room temperature. A 0.5 mm diameter 23 cm long Pt wire ring and a RE-1BP type Ag/AgCl reference electrode with a ceramic junction filled with 3 M NaCl electrolyte ($+0.195\text{ V}$ vs. reference hydrogen electrode) were used as counter and reference electrodes, respectively. The samples were cut, and one side was mirror-polished for the as-cast and after TPN states. In order to block the signal, the back side of the samples was painted with nail varnish. The immersed areas of the samples were $0.093 \pm 0.006\text{ cm}^2$ (as-cast), $0.041 \pm 0.008\text{ cm}^2$ (TPN glass and oxide layer), and $0.118 \pm 0.005\text{ cm}^2$ (TPN crystallized and oxide layer), as determined by an Olympus BX51 Fluorescence Microscope using the Olympus Stream Motion 1.9.3. software – Extended Focal Imaging feature and area calculation function. The electrochemical measurements were performed with a Gamry Interface 1010E Potentiostat/Galvanostat/ZRA. Before the experiments, the open circuit potential (OCP) was measured for 3600 s to stabilize the working electrode–electrolyte interface. Electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) was performed at OCP at an AC amplitude of 10 mV recorded from 100,000 to 0.01 Hz. Afterwards, linear sweep voltammetry (LSV) was conducted with the same electrodes. The forward scan ran at 1 mV s^{-1} ranged from -0.3 V vs. OCP until $+1.5\text{ V}$ vs. Ag/AgCl or until the current density reached 0.01 A cm^{-2} . The reverse scans were also conducted using the same parameters but excluded from the results because repassivation was not attained in any of the samples. At least two tests were performed for each composition and electrolyte for statistical information.

2.2.4. Contact angle measurements

Static water contact angle measurements were conducted on a DSA 100 (Drop Shape Analysis System) from Krüss GmbH via the sessile drop method on the etched surface of the as-cast and TPN $Ti_{40}Zr_{10}Cu_{36}Pd_{14}$ BMGs. De-ionized water droplets with a volume of $2\text{ }\mu\text{L}$ were placed on the surface of the samples by an automated deposition procedure and their contact angle with the solid surface were recorded and analyzed using the embedded high-resolution camera and the specialized software of the measuring device. Two different holding substrates were employed to align the samples properly as the small surface area made the contact angle measurements challenging to carry out. The contact angles were measured after 10 s deposition and then in appropriate time intervals until 60 s. The results are presented in the form of 10 s and the time dependent value after 60 s, accordingly. For each sample, the average of 5 measurements was taken.

2.3. In vitro cytocompatibility evaluation

2.3.1. Cell cultivation

Human gingival fibroblast cells (HGF) were purchased from Promo Cell (PCS-201-018) and cultivated in minimal essential medium eagle-alpha modification (α -MEM, Sigma-Aldrich) supplemented with 10% fetal bovine serum (FBS, Sigma-Aldrich) and 1% antibiotics at 310 K, 5% CO_2 atmosphere. The cells were cultivated until 80%–90% confluence, detached by a trypsin-EDTA solution (0.25% in phosphate buffer solution – PBS), harvested and used for the experiments.

2.3.2. Cytocompatibility evaluation

The cells were directly seeded onto the specimens' surface (2 mm diameter) at a defined density (2000 cells/sample), and after 4 h of allowing adhesion, 300 μL of culture media was added to each sample. Subsequently, they were cultivated for 24 and 48 h; at each time point, the viability of the cells was evaluated by means of their metabolic activity using the resazurin colorimetric metabolic assay (alamarBlue™, ready-to-use solution from Life Technologies) by directly adding the dye solution (0.015% in PBS) onto the wells containing specimens. After 4 h of incubation in the dark, the fluorescent signals (expressed as relative fluorescent units – RFU) were detected at 590 nm by a spectrophotometer (Spark, Tecan, Switzerland). Moreover, the fluorescent Live/Dead assay was applied to visually check for viable cells (Live/Dead, Viability/ Cytotoxicity Kit for mammalian cells, Invitrogen) with a digital EVOS FLoid microscope (Life Technologies). Finally, the morphology of the cells was visually investigated by scanning electron microscopy (SEM, JSM-IT500, JEOL). Briefly, specimens were dehydrated by the alcohol scale (70–90% ethanol, 1 h each and 100% for 2 h), swelled with hexamethyldisilazane, mounted onto stubs with carbon tape and metalized with gold for 2 min (smart coater, JEOL). Images were collected at different magnifications ($\times 200$ and $\times 500$) using a secondary electron detector.

2.4. Statistical analysis of data

The experiments were performed in triplicate, and the results were statistically analyzed using the SPSS software (v.20.0, IBM, USA). First, the data normal distribution and the homogeneity of the variance were confirmed by Shapiro-Wilk's and Levene's tests, respectively; then, groups were compared by the one-way ANOVA using Tukey's test as post-hoc analysis. Significant differences were established at p-values < 0.05 .

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Structural and compositional characterization

Synchrotron XRD patterns of $Ti_{40}Zr_{10}Cu_{36}Pd_{14}$ as-cast, TPN glass, and TPN composite are shown in Fig. 1. The patterns of $Ti_{40}Zr_{10}Cu_{36}Pd_{14}$ as-cast and TPN glass signify a glassy nature. However, the

Fig. 1. Synchrotron XRD measurements of three selected samples (i.e., as-cast, TPN glass, and TPN composite) in reciprocal space. The diffraction patterns of TPN composite delineate the evolution of B2-TiZr, $CuTi_2$, $CuTi_3$, and Cu_3Ti_2 .

second sharp diffraction peak of the TPN glass is deconvoluted into two peaks, indicating structural modifications. Hence, it can be concluded that the applied thermomechanical driving force during the TPN process can induce structural heterogeneities [23]. On the pattern of the TPN composite, crystalline diffraction peaks corresponding to the B2-TiZr, CuTi₂, CuTi₃, and Cu₃Ti₂ phases are superimposed. Exploring the structure reveals that spherulites surrounded by semi-crystalline outer shells are formed in the glassy matrix. These shells act as a synergy between order and disorder in the structure. Larger needle-shaped Cu₃Ti₂ phases precipitate in the center of the spherulites. To these phases, finer needles of tetragonal CuTi attach at 90°. Rather at the center of spherulites, CuTi₃ of a few percent might form during solidification upon eutectic reactions as the cooling rate is kept at its threshold during casting in order to cast the largest possible BMG. B2-TiZr is present primarily in mature spherulites. It nucleates in the vicinity of the tetragonal CuTi crystals and grows in all directions to the shell. This grants the spherical shape to the spherulites [24].

The surface of the TPNed Ti₄₀Zr₁₀Cu₃₆Pd₁₄ BMG was further studied by STEM-EDX to demonstrate the distinction between the surfaces and the interior regions, as the surface is what cells come in contact to and thus is important for cytocompatibility. The elemental distributions of the both regions shown in Fig. 2 indicate a clear change in the elemental compositions between the interior of the alloys and their surface. This change was quantified via EDX line scans. The analyzed region is indicated by a horizontal dashed line in the electron image in Fig. 2. The transition between the bulk material towards the oxidized surface is accompanied by Pd enrichment, followed by an enrichment of O, Zr, Cu, and Ti towards the sample surface and thus a depletion of Pd. The surface layer of ~100 nm possibly consists of Ti, Cu, and Zr oxides. Underneath, a Pd-enriched interface is observed, towards which the oxidation kinetics is controlled by oxygen diffusion in the scale. This interfacial Pd layer acts as a barrier to further oxygen diffusion. The elemental maps and line scans of the composite alloy detect more or less the same oxide formation as on the glassy alloy (Supplementary data, Fig. S1). It should be noted that the TEM-EDX line scans lead to an overestimation of the at.% of Cu because the lamellae were mounted onto a Cu grid. The trend, however, is still noticeable across the oxidized surface.

3.2. Thermomechanical properties

The structural relaxation kinetics and crystallization behavior of Ti₄₀Zr₁₀Cu₃₆Pd₁₄ as the key events upon shaping were evaluated by a sensitive frequency-dependent DMA technique in 3-point bending (TPB) mode at room and elevated temperatures, which allows to gain more insight into the impact of thermoplastic net-shaping under the given conditions [25]. Usually, when compared with "static" experiments such as DSC/TMA, dynamic glass transition temperature (T_g) is a highly frequency-dependent parameter. In comparison to tension- and torsion-type measurements, TPB is more sensitive to structural changes around T_g and thus advantageous to visualize the effects [26]. As a hypothesis, the oscillation of the individual mobile species via TPB transforms into a more cooperative oscillation of a large group of mobile species by a percolation process with the same phase [27]. This can incorporate an ordering of atoms, leading to elastic stiffening of the BMGs. Unlike the TPB mode, tension- and torsion-induced free volume in the structure during DMA is hardly conducive to relaxation of the system. In this case, each atom practically oscillates around its own position with its own phase. That would lead to a structural rearrangement in the medium- and short-range order because the distance between the atoms is larger than the range of the damped oscillation. And thus, a cooperative oscillatory relaxation with the same phase is hence barely possible in the system. Fig. 3a illustrates the storage modulus (G'), the loss modulus (G''), and the loss factor ($\tan \delta$) of the glassy Ti₄₀Zr₁₀Cu₃₆Pd₁₄. At temperatures below the glass transition, the considered BMG deforms primarily elastic, and the mechanical response is independent of the testing frequency, whereas higher temperatures and lower frequencies around the supercooled liquid region (SCLR) promote atomic mobility. This is manifested by the glass transition events taking place at higher temperatures when the frequency increases from 0.1 to 10 Hz. In contrast, the frequency does not seem to have that much effect on the onset temperature of crystallization (T_x) as it varies from 0.1 to 10 Hz. T_g of the traces is marked by a sudden change in the slope of G' , which yields values of 649, 662, and 668 K \pm 1 for the given frequencies. G' of 0.1 Hz drops drastically beyond T_g to its absolute minimum value of 47 \pm 1 GPa at the onset of crystallization ($T_{x1} = 692 \pm 1$ K). In G' , the

Fig. 2. Cross-sectional TEM-EDX analyses showing a variation of the elemental compositions between the interior (left part) and the oxidized surface of the as-cast Ti₄₀Zr₁₀Cu₃₆Pd₁₄ glass, including elemental maps of Ti, Zr, Cu, Pd, and O; together with line-scans across the transition between the interior and surface region (extracted from the white dashed line in the electron image).

Fig. 3. (a) Storage modulus (G'), loss modulus (G''), and loss factor ($\tan \delta$) of the cast $\text{Ti}_{40}\text{Zr}_{10}\text{Cu}_{36}\text{Pd}_{14}$ glass as a function of temperature. The measurement frequencies were 0.1 to 1 to 10 Hz, and the heating rate was 10 K/min. The T_{α} measurements at different frequencies result in a linear Arrhenius behavior with a slope of 8.6 ± 1.9 eV obtained from the slope of the linear fit (b).

onsets of the increase after the first and second sharp drops correspond to T_{X1} and T_{X2} , respectively, at 692 and 775 K ± 1 . In G'' and $\tan \delta$, the two maxima are associated with a two-stage glass crystallization. Stiffening owing to β -relaxation is observed at 1 and 10 Hz prior to the glass transition. The small hump in the evolution of G'' depicted in the inset of Fig. 3a indicates relaxation in the γ region. Structural relaxations occur as the temperature rises, leading to an increase in G' during β -relaxation and a decrease in G' during α -relaxation processes. A driving frequency of 0.1 Hz, compared to 1 and 10 Hz, can clearly visualize the crystallization events. After full crystallization, the G' of 1 and 10 Hz exceed their values of the initial states. The variations in the frequency-dependent T_{α} values are quantified in an Arrhenius plot, revealing an activation energy of $E_a = 8.6 \pm 1.9$ eV (830 ± 183 kJ/mol) attributed to α -relaxation [27–29] (Fig. 3b). This high value is indicative of collective motion of a large number of atoms in this BMG [30–32]. These observations corroborate an accessible SCLR in which the material can be shaped to oral implants [33,34]. G' shows relaxations in the β region at 1 and 10 Hz. This relaxation is minimal at 0.1 Hz. T_{β} found from the intersection of the extrapolated tangent lines shifts to higher temperatures with increasing frequencies, depicted in Fig. S2. The activation energy estimated from these points yields 371 ± 43 kJ/mol, depicted in Fig. S3.

Fig. 4 displays the evolution of G' , G'' , and $\tan \delta$ of the deformed $\text{Ti}_{40}\text{Zr}_{10}\text{Cu}_{36}\text{Pd}_{14}$ specimens in the glassy and composite states. In G'' of 0.1 Hz, the peak maxima can be addressed to T_{X1} and T_{X2} , for which values of 723 ± 1 and 777 ± 1 K for the TPN glass are registered. T_{X1} of the TPN composite yields an ascending value of 727 ± 1 K, and T_{X2} of the TPN composite has the same value as T_{X1} . The frequencies of 1 and 10 Hz show an evident alleviation of the crystallization events (G'' and $\tan \delta$ of Fig. 4a and b). Fig. 4c illustrates the G' , G'' , and $\tan \delta$ measurements of the as-cast, TPN glass, and TPN composite samples at 0.1 Hz. G' of the as-cast material displays a plateau up to T_g (649 ± 1 K); then the intact elastic structure breaks up, by which G' drops to its minimum of 47 ± 1 GPa at T_{X1} (692 ± 1 K) and rises to 71 ± 1 GPa at 716 ± 1 K, followed by a second drop to 58 ± 1 GPa at T_{X2} (775 ± 1 K). G' increases afterwards

to 82 ± 1 GPa at 789 ± 1 K and decreases to 77 ± 1 GPa at 798 ± 1 K. The characteristic events in the evolution of G'' and $\tan \delta$ of the TPN glass and the TPN composite are mitigated compared to those of the as-cast alloy. The onset of the sudden increase in the slope of G'' and $\tan \delta$ in the course of heating can be linked to T_{α} , which is shifted towards higher temperatures in the TPN glass and the TPN composite. This confirms a higher thermomechanical stability of the processed glasses at elevated temperatures. In TPN glass and composite, the effects on G' are compensated, which is probably due to the overlap between the glass transition and crystallization events minimizing the drop in G' . Fig. 4d illustrates the corresponding dilatometer traces. The dilatation curve of the as-cast material is basically linear at lower temperatures until the onset of structural relaxation at 493 ± 1 K, where thermal expansion starts to counteract with contraction, which saturates around 550 ± 1 K [17]. The ordinate signal remains more or less constant during the transition into the supercooled liquid state and thereafter until the first crystallization is reached, which is indicated by a step-like drop in the signal within $706 - 724 \pm 1$ K. Afterwards, the glass continues to expand obeying nearly the same thermal expansion coefficient as below 493 K [17]. It is worth noting that the absolute length variations are not universal as they can be affected by the geometry of the specimens and the test domain. Compared to the as-cast state sample, TPN glass and composite samples are relaxed and thus shows stronger resistance towards expansion/contraction. A further penetration step occurs at 792 ± 1 K as the glass crystallizes in the second stage until 812 ± 1 K. The two-stage crystallization pathway traversed in the as-cast glass is smoothed and drops to a single-stage after TPN, which is also confirmed by DMA by the disappearance of the T_{X1} peak. Hence, G' of the TPN samples is stabilized up to 723 ± 1 K, whereas G'' of the as-cast drops at 623 ± 1 K.

3.3. Corrosion activity

The linear sweep polarization graphs in Fig. 5a indicate clear

Fig. 4. Evolution of the storage modulus (G'), the loss modulus (G''), and the loss factor ($\tan \delta$) with temperature during continuous heating (10 K/min) from 300 K to 850 K at a fixed frequency of 0.1 Hz of (a) TPN glass, (b) TPN composite, and (c) the comparison. The corresponding dilatometer traces are depicted in (d).

Fig. 5. (a) Potentiodynamic polarization graphs of different state samples with and without oxide layers. Note that the standard deviation of E_{corr} is within ± 1 mV, whereas for J_{corr} , the deviation is within 0.025% of the measured data. The reference potential has a redox potential of $+0.195$ V vs. a reference hydrogen electrode. (b) Bode magnitude plots of the corresponding sample at their open circuit potential.

differences between different states of the material, as well as the oxide formation upon TPN. The as-cast state of the $\text{Ti}_{40}\text{Zr}_{10}\text{Cu}_{36}\text{Pd}_{14}$ BMG has a corrosion potential, E_{corr} , of -62 ± 4 mV with a corresponding corrosion current density, J_{corr} , of $15.1 \pm 0.7 \mu\text{A cm}^{-2}$. For long-waiting times, the sample crystallizes under TPN conditions, which leads to a shift of E_{corr} towards more negative potentials (i.e., -411 ± 2 mV), where J_{corr} also increases ($24.4 \pm 1.0 \mu\text{A cm}^{-2}$).

After TPN, provided that the amorphous state is retained, E_{corr} gets closer to zero (-12 ± 2 mV) with a huge drop in $J_{\text{corr}} = 0.03 \pm 0.002 \mu\text{A cm}^{-2}$. The shift of the corrosion potential towards more positive values favors the formation of a protective surface, leading to a slowdown in corrosion rate [35]. The drop in the corrosion current density by two orders of magnitude confirms a very high stability of this state in 0.9 wt% saline environment. Similarly, the passivation current density, J_{pass} , of the TPN glass samples is only $0.14 \pm 0.007 \mu\text{A cm}^{-2}$, i.e., much lower than that of the as-cast state ($\sim 1250 \pm 60 \mu\text{A cm}^{-2}$). Compared to the TPN glass, the TPN samples with an oxide layer formed upon TPN show much more negative E_{corr} values (-563 ± 2 and -430 ± 5 mV for the amorphous and composite specimens, respectively), with similar J_{corr} values (43 ± 3 and $46 \pm 3 \mu\text{A cm}^{-2}$, respectively) which is 2 orders of magnitude larger. This finding also indicates that corrosion happens much faster in oxide-layer-containing samples.

The frequency-dependent Bode magnitude plots of the samples in Fig. 5b show an agreement with the results obtained from LSV. The TPN glass displays the largest $|Z|$ ($\sim 6437 \pm 193 \text{ k}\Omega \text{ cm}^2$) which can be accounted for the lowest J_{corr} . This value is only $\sim 2 \pm 0.06 \text{ k}\Omega \text{ cm}^2$ for the as-cast state, i.e., about 3200 times lower. The composite structure in the other three sample types leads to a small Bode magnitude with a clear hump observed at low to medium-range frequencies. Due to the enhanced corrosion properties of the as-cast glass with respect to the TPN composite counterparts, the following contact angle and cytocompatibility analysis was performed using the TPN glass and its oxide layer.

3.4. Contact angle measurements

The results from the static water contact angle measurements conducted on the etched surface of the as-cast and TPN $\text{Ti}_{40}\text{Zr}_{10}\text{Cu}_{36}\text{Pd}_{14}$ BMGs are shown in Table 1. The TPN $\text{Ti}_{40}\text{Zr}_{10}\text{Cu}_{36}\text{Pd}_{14}$ BMG is investigated both on the oxidized and polished sides. The water contact angle values of the specimens are close to each other; however, a slight decrease of the oxidized surface can be observed. The close values observed for the surfaces can be linked to the similar hydrophobic character of the surface oxides, c.f. Cu oxide for the as-cast vs. mixture of

Table 1

Water contact angle data of the as-cast and TPN $\text{Ti}_{40}\text{Zr}_{10}\text{Cu}_{36}\text{Pd}_{14}$ BMG.

	Mean/ $^{\circ}$	SD/ $^{\circ}$
as-cast	96.8	2.1
TPN glass	100.2	1.8
TPN glass oxide	94.9	2.4

Ti, Cu and Zr oxides for the TPN oxide. After polishing (TPN glass), the surface hydrophobicity increases, which could be due to the Ti-rich, Zr- and Pd-containing native oxide layer with Ti:Zr:Pd ratio of 6.2:1.8:1 in at.% attained from X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy analysis (unpublished data). The increase in surface hydrophobicity can be also correlated with the decrease in corrosion rates and increase in surface resistivity as confirmed in section 2.3.

3.5. Cytocompatibility study

The effect of the formed oxide layer at the surfaces of $\text{Ti}_{40}\text{Zr}_{10}\text{Cu}_{36}\text{Pd}_{14}$ TPN glass specimens on HGF cells was evaluated by comparing their cytocompatibility properties with the TPN glass without oxide layer and the as-cast $\text{Ti}_{40}\text{Zr}_{10}\text{Cu}_{36}\text{Pd}_{14}$ glass (control sample). This evaluation was preliminarily performed *in vitro* on HGF cells selected as a representative of the soft tissue in contact with implants that replaced the dental cavity as it represents a physical hurdle for bacteria invasion [36]. Accordingly, HGF cells were directly seeded on the samples' surfaces, and after 24 and 48 h, the viability and the morphology of adhered and spread cells were determined by fluorescent Live/Dead assay and SEM imaging, respectively (Fig. 6b). The metabolic activity of the cells was evaluated using the colorimetric resazurin assay (Alamar blue); the results are reported in Fig. 6a, indicating that the metabolism of cells was comparable between TPN with an oxide layer and TPN without an oxide layer and as-cast samples at both 24/48 h time-points. A statistically significant difference was observed for the TPN samples with an oxide layer after 48 h in comparison to the TPN specimens without an oxide layer and the control samples ($p < 0.05$ indicated by *, Fig. 6a). As a confirmation of the cells' metabolic activity results, the images obtained from the Live/Dead assay and SEM demonstrate that the cells were able to successfully adhere and spread onto the $\text{Ti}_{40}\text{Zr}_{10}\text{Cu}_{36}\text{Pd}_{14}$ -TPN with oxide layer surfaces; however, on the surfaces of TPN specimens without oxide layer and as-cast samples some cells are in round shapes and the confluence of these roundish cells onto the TPN samples without oxide layer is more pronounced than for the ones on the control specimens. The surface wettability of the as-cast $\text{Ti}_{40}\text{Zr}_{10}\text{Cu}_{36}\text{Pd}_{14}$ BMG

Fig. 6. Cytocompatibility evaluation of $\text{Ti}_{40}\text{Zr}_{10}\text{Cu}_{36}\text{Pd}_{14}$ TPN glass specimens with and without oxide layer towards HGF that were seeded directly onto their surfaces. $\text{Ti}_{40}\text{Zr}_{10}\text{Cu}_{36}\text{Pd}_{14}$ BMG (as-cast) was considered as control sample. The cytocompatibility activity after 24 and 48 h was evaluated by: a) metabolic activity after 24 and 48 h; b) upper panel: Fluorescent Live/Dead images of the surface attached cells after 48 h; scale bars are 100 μm ; bottom panel: SEM images of the surface attached cells after 48 h at two different magnifications $\times 200$ (scale bar 100 μm) and $\times 500$ (scale bar 50 μm). * indicates p value < 0.05 .

has been previously investigated by Rezvan et al. [17] as a favorable surface for its antifouling properties. One would expect that the same surface with hydrophobic characteristics is not favorable for direct attachment of cells on the surface. Of course, this does not mean that the surface is cytotoxic, since the green color of those cells in the fluorescent Live/Dead assay demonstrates that the cells were alive. The same behavior with no significant differences is observed for the TPNed non-oxide layer. This means that the thermoplastic net-shaping, an important process to give the BMGs their final shape as implants, does not adversely affect the cytocompatibility (Fig. 6b). EDX-TEM investigations of the oxide layer of the TPNed samples, on the other hand, show an enrichment of Ti, Zr, Cu and the presence of oxygen towards the surface, meaning that a mix of Ti, Cu, and Zr oxides is present. Indeed, the presence of titanium oxide could significantly enhance the surface wettability, thereby favoring cells attachment, as previously demonstrated by Wang et al. [37]. This could justify the better performance of the oxide layer in easing cell attachment.

4. Conclusions

The prospects of $\text{Ti}_{40}\text{Zr}_{10}\text{Cu}_{36}\text{Pd}_{14}$ BMG as oral implant material are advanced in the aspects of processing, structure-dependent mechanical performance, corrosion, hydrophobicity, and bioactivity. In this study we have investigated the effect of thermoplastic net-shaping, the process required to reach the final desired shape of the implants, on the BMG's microstructure, corrosion behavior, and cytocompatibility. It is

confirmed by DMA that optimized thermoplastic processing leads to BMGs and BMG composites showing a more stabilized G' up to ~ 700 K, revealing an increase in the thermomechanical stability by above 100 K in comparison to the as-cast glass. In 0.9 wt% NaCl solution, corrosion is strongly inhibited in the TPNed glass determined from ~ 4 orders of magnitude lower J_{corr} values as well as two orders of magnitude larger $|Z|$ at low-frequencies compared to the as-cast material. A cytocompatibility analysis was conducted by seeding HGF cells directly onto the oxide-layer-containing and oxide-layer-free $\text{Ti}_{40}\text{Zr}_{10}\text{Cu}_{36}\text{Pd}_{14}$ BMGs after thermoplastic net-shaping, using the as-cast $\text{Ti}_{40}\text{Zr}_{10}\text{Cu}_{36}\text{Pd}_{14}$ BMG as control. The results demonstrate that thermoplastic net-shaping does not adversely affect the cytocompatibility. On the other hand, the formation of ~ 100 nm thin surface layers consisting of Ti, Cu, and Zr oxides improves cells attachment. The attributing factor for this improvement is related to the presence of titanium oxide on the surface that significantly improves the surface wettability.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Amir Rezvan: Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Visualization, Validation, Writing – original draft. **Elham Sharifikolouei:** Methodology, Validation, Writing – original draft. **Viktor Soprunyuk:** Investigation, Writing – review & editing. **Wilfried Schranz:** Resources, Writing – review & editing. **Juraj Todt:** Investigation, Writing – review & editing. **Alice Lassnig:** Investigation, Writing – review & editing, Funding acquisition. **Christoph Gammer:** Resources, Writing – review

& editing. **Nikolaus August Sifferlinger**: Writing – review & editing. **Atacan Ascı**: Investigation. **Ilya Okulov**: Writing – review & editing. **Sandra Schlögl**: Investigation, Writing – review & editing. **Jozef Keckes**: Resources, Funding acquisition. **Ziba Najmi**: Methodology, Investigation, Writing – review & editing. **Andrea Cochis**: Writing – review & editing. **Alessandro Calogero Scalia**: Writing – review & editing. **Lia Rimondini**: Supervision, Writing – review & editing. **Baran Sarac**: Conceptualization, Methodology, Validation, Writing – original draft, Supervision, Funding acquisition. **Jürgen Eckert**: Supervision, Writing – review & editing, Resources, Funding acquisition.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

The data required to produce these findings cannot be shared at this time as it also forms parts of an ongoing study.

Acknowledgments

B.S. acknowledges the Austrian Science Fund (FWF) under project grant I3937-N36. E.S. would like to thank European Commission for providing funding for this project under the Horizon 2020 research and innovation program for Marie Skłodowska-Curie Individual Fellowship, with the acronym “MAGIC” and grant agreement N. 892050. A.L. acknowledges financial support by the Austrian Science Fund (FWF) under the project grant T891-N36, Y1236-N37. Additional support was provided through the ERC Proof of Concept Grant TriboMetGlass (grant ERC-2019-PoC-862485). We acknowledge DESY (Hamburg, Germany), a member of the Helmholtz Association HGF, for the provision of experimental facilities. Parts of this research were carried out at PETRA III and we would like to thank Dr. Nobert Schell and Dr. Emad Maawad for assistance in using beamline P07B, operated by Helmholtz Zentrum Hereon. Authors thank Siavash Amirosoo and Katja Hrbinič for their assistance in the water contact angle measurements.

Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.matdes.2023.112256>.

References

- [1] J. Schroers, T.M. Hodges, G. Kumar, H. Raman, A.J. Barnes, Q. Pham, T.A. Waniuk, Thermoplastic blow molding of metals, *Mater. Today* 14 (2011) 14–19, [https://doi.org/10.1016/S1369-7021\(11\)70018-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1369-7021(11)70018-9).
- [2] B. Sarac, J. Eckert, Thermoplasticity of metallic glasses: Processing and applications, *Prog. Mater. Sci.* 127 (2022), 100941, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pmatsci.2022.100941>.
- [3] J. Schroers, The superplastic forming of bulk metallic glasses, *JOM* 57 (2005) 35–39, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11837-005-0093-2>.
- [4] B. Sarac, G. Kumar, T. Hodges, S.Y. Ding, A. Desai, J. Schroers, Three-dimensional shell fabrication using blow molding of bulk metallic glass, *J. Microelectromech. Syst.* 20 (2011) 28–36, <https://doi.org/10.1109/JMEMS.2010.2090495>.
- [5] B. Sarac, S. Bera, S. Balakin, M. Stoica, M. Calin, J. Eckert, Hierarchical surface patterning of Ni- and Be-free Ti- and Zr-based bulk metallic glasses by thermoplastic net-shaping, *Mater. Sci. Eng. C* 73 (2017) 398–405, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.msec.2016.12.059>.
- [6] J. Schroers, Processing of bulk metallic glass, *Adv. Mater.* 22 (2010) 1566–1597, <https://doi.org/10.1002/adma.200902776>.
- [7] M. Hasan, J. Schroers, G. Kumar, Functionalization of metallic glasses through hierarchical patterning, *Nano Lett.* 15 (2015) 963–968, <https://doi.org/10.1021/nl504694s>.
- [8] B. Sarac, S. Bera, F. Spieckermann, S. Balakin, M. Stoica, M. Calin, J. Eckert, Micropatterning kinetics of different glass-forming systems investigated by thermoplastic net-shaping, *Scr. Mater.* 137 (2017) 127–131, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scriptamat.2017.02.038>.
- [9] G. Kumar, A. Desai, J. Schroers, Bulk metallic glass: The smaller the better, *Adv. Mater.* 23 (2011) 461–476, <https://doi.org/10.1002/adma.201002148>.
- [10] G.S. Leventhal, Titanium, a metal for surgery, *J. Bone Joint Surg. Am.* 33 (1951) 473–474.
- [11] H.F. Li, Y.F. Zheng, Recent advances in bulk metallic glasses for biomedical applications, *Acta Biomater.* 36 (2016) 1–20, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.actbio.2016.03.047>.
- [12] C.Y. Xie, I. Milosev, F.U. Renner, A. Kokalj, P. Bruna, D. Crespo, Corrosion resistance of crystalline and amorphous CuZr alloys in NaCl aqueous environment and effect of corrosion inhibitors, *J. Alloy. Compd.* 879 (2021), 160464, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jallcom.2021.160464>.
- [13] M.M. Vasić, T. Žák, N. Pizúrová, I.S. Simatović, D.M. Minić, Influence of Thermal Treatment on Microstructure and Corrosion Behavior of Amorphous Fe₄₀Ni₄₀B₁₂Si₈ Alloy, *Metall. Mater. Trans. A* 52 (2021) 34–45, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11661-020-06079-3>.
- [14] E. Yüce, L. Zarazúa-Villalobos, B. Ter-Ovanesian, E. Sharifikolouei, Z. Najmi, F. Spieckermann, J. Eckert, B. Sarac, New-generation biocompatible Ti-based metallic glass ribbons for flexible implants, *Mater. Des.* 223 (2022), 111139, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.matdes.2022.111139>.
- [15] M. Katsikogianni, Y.F. Missirlis, Concise review of mechanisms of bacterial adhesion to biomaterials and of techniques used in estimating bacteria-material interactions, *Eur. Cell Mater.* 8 (2004) 37–57, <https://doi.org/10.22203/ecm.v008a05>.
- [16] E. Sharifikolouei, Z. Najmi, A. Cochis, A.C. Scalia, M. Aliabadi, S. Perero, L. Rimondini, Generation of cytocompatible superhydrophobic Zr–Cu–Ag metallic glass coatings with antifouling properties for medical textiles, *Mater. Today Bio* 12 (2021), 100148, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mtbio.2021.100148>.
- [17] A. Rezvan, E. Sharifikolouei, A. Lassnig, V. Soprnyuk, C. Gammer, F. Spieckermann, W. Schranz, Z. Najmi, A. Cochis, A.C. Scalia, L. Rimondini, M. Manfredi, J. Eckert, B. Sarac, Antibacterial activity, cytocompatibility, and thermomechanical stability of Ti₄₀Zr₁₀Cu₃₆Pd₁₄ bulk metallic glass, *Mater. Today Bio* 16 (2022), 100378, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mtbio.2022.100378>.
- [18] S.L. Zhu, X.M. Wang, F.X. Qin, M. Yoshimura, A. Inoue, New TiZrCuPd Quaternary Bulk Glassy Alloys with Potential of Biomedical Applications, *Mater. Trans.* 48 (2007) 2445–2448, <https://doi.org/10.2320/matertrans.MRA2007086>.
- [19] F.X. Qin, M. Yoshimura, X.M. Wang, S.L. Zhu, A. Kawashima, K. Asami, A. Inoue, Corrosion Behavior of a Ti-based bulk metallic glass and its crystalline alloys, *Mater. Trans.* 48 (2007) 1855–1858, <https://doi.org/10.2320/matertrans.MJ200713>.
- [20] G. Lütjering, Property optimization through microstructural control in titanium and aluminum alloys, *Mater. Sci. Eng., A* 263 (1999) 117–126, [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0921-5093\(98\)01169-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0921-5093(98)01169-1).
- [21] P. Gong, L. Deng, J. Jin, S. Wang, X. Wang, K. Yao, Review on the Research and Development of Ti-Based Bulk Metallic Glasses, *Metals-Basel* 6 (2016) 264, <https://doi.org/10.3390/met6110264>.
- [22] G. Ashiotis, A. Deschildre, Z. Nawaz, J.P. Wright, D. Karkoulis, F.E. Picca, J. Kieffer, The fast azimuthal integration Python library: pyFAI, *J. Appl. Cryst.* 48 (2015) 510–519, <https://doi.org/10.1107/S1600576715004306>.
- [23] J.C. Qiao, Q. Wang, J.M. Pelletier, H. Kato, R. Casalini, D. Crespo, E. Pineda, Y. Yao, Y. Yang, Structural heterogeneities and mechanical behavior of amorphous alloys, *Prog. Mater. Sci.* 104 (2019) 250–329, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pmatsci.2019.04.005>.
- [24] L. Gautier, S. Cazottes, M. Veron, D. Fabregue, J. Chevalier, Spherulitic growth process in Ti-based metallic glass: Microstructure, phase identification, and growth mechanism, *Mater. Charact.* 192 (2022), 112170, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.matchar.2022.112170>.
- [25] A. Rezvan, B. Sarac, V. Soprnyuk, J.T. Kim, K.K. Song, C.J. Li, W. Schranz, J. Eckert, Influence of combinatorial annealing and plastic deformation treatments on the intrinsic properties of Cu₄₆Zr₄₆Al₈ bulk metallic glass, *Intermetallics* 127 (2020), 106986, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.intermet.2020.106986>.
- [26] A. Rezvan, B. Sarac, V. Soprnyuk, F. Spieckermann, C. Gammer, H. Sheng, N. A. Sifferlinger, J. Eckert, Deformation-Mode-Sensitive Behavior of CuZr-Based Bulk Metallic Glasses Under Dynamic Loading, *Metall. Mater. Trans. A* 52 (2021) 8–13, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11661-020-06048-w>.
- [27] J.M. Pelletier, J. Perez, L. Duffrene, Mechanical response of an oxide glass to mechanical loading—shear and volume relaxation effects: physical analysis, *Acta Mater.* 48 (2000) 1397–1408, [https://doi.org/10.1016/S1359-6454\(99\)00387-0](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1359-6454(99)00387-0).
- [28] J.C. Qiao, J.M. Pelletier, Dynamic Mechanical Relaxation in Bulk Metallic Glasses: A Review, *J. Mater. Sci. Technol.* 30 (2014) 523–545, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jmst.2014.04.018>.
- [29] Q. Wang, J.M. Pelletier, J.J. Blandin, Thermal stability of cerium-based bulk metallic glasses. Influence of iron addition, *J. Alloy Compd.* 504 (2010) 357–361, [doi: 10.1016/j.jallcom.2010.05.070](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jallcom.2010.05.070).
- [30] K. Schröter, G. Wilde, R. Willnecker, M. Weiss, K. Samwer, E. Donth, Shear modulus and compliance in the range of the dynamic glass transition for metallic glasses, *Eur. Phys. J. B* 5 (1998) 1–5, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s100510050411>.
- [31] S. Etienne, J.Y. Cavallé, J. Perez, R. Point, M. Salvia, Automatic System for Analysis of Micromechanical Properties Rev, *Sci. Instrum.* 53 (1982) 1261–1266, <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.1137153>.
- [32] S. Puech, J.J. Blandin, J.L. Soubeyroux, Mg based bulk metallic glasses with high mechanical strength and large viscoplastic forming capacity, *Adv. Eng. Mater.* 9 (2007) 764–768, <https://doi.org/10.1002/adem.200700160>.
- [33] S. Maeda, T. Yamasaki, Y. Yokoyama, D. Okai, T. Fukami, H.M. Kimura, A. Inoue, Viscosity measurements of Zr₅₅Cu₃₀Al₁₀Ni₅ and Zr₅₀Cu_{40-x}Al₁₀Pd_x (x=0, 3 and 7 at.%) supercooled liquid alloys by using a penetration viscometer, *Mater. Sci. Eng., A* 449 (2007) 203–206, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.msea.2006.02.288>.

- [34] A. Inoue, Stabilization of metallic supercooled liquid and bulk amorphous alloys, *Acta Mater.* 48 (2000) 279–306, [https://doi.org/10.1016/S1359-6454\(99\)00300-6](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1359-6454(99)00300-6).
- [35] F. Ropital, 15 - Environmental degradation in hydrocarbon fuel processing plant: issues and mitigation, in: M.R. Khan (Ed.), *Advances in Clean Hydrocarbon Fuel Processing*, Woodhead Publishing, Sawston, United Kingdom, 2011, pp. 437–462.
- [36] A. Cochis, S. Ferraris, R. Sorrentino, B. Azzimonti, C. Novara, F. Geobaldo, F. Truffa Giachet, C. Vineis, A. Varesano, A. Sayed Abdelgeliel, S. Spriano, L. Rimondini, Silver-doped keratin nanofibers preserve a titanium surface from biofilm contamination and favor soft-tissue healing, *J. Mater. Chem. B* 5 (2017) 8366–8377, <https://doi.org/10.1039/C7TB01965C>.
- [37] G. Wang, J. Li, K. Lv, W. Zhang, X. Ding, G. Yang, X. Liu, X. Jiang, Surface thermal oxidation on titanium implants to enhance osteogenic activity and in vivo osseointegration, *Sci. Rep.* 6 (2016) 31769, <https://doi.org/10.1038/srep31769>.